

Influence of aluminosilicates and their modified forms on properties of composite materials

B. Pecušová¹, M. Pajtášová², A. Prnová^{3,4}, J. Valúchová^{3,4}

¹ Central Laboratories, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: beata.pecusova@tnuni.sk)

² Faculty of Industrial Technologies in Púchov, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín,

³ VILLA – Joined Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FchPT STU, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

⁴ VILLA, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Influence of aluminosilicates and their modified forms on properties of composite materials (especially rubber blends) was studied in this work. Modified Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} forms were prepared from commercial bentonite, kaolin and illite based clay products. On the second step, organomodified forms were prepared by intercalating the organic molecules of dithiophosphate and benzthiazole sulfur vulcanization accelerators. Clay products and their modified and organomodified forms were studied and characterized by thermal gravimetric (TG/DTG) analysis (Fig.1), infrared (IR)spectroscopy (Fig.2) and X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) analysis (Fig.3).

Fig. 1 TG and DTG curves of bentonite sample P 130 and its modified forms a) P 130, b) P 130 Co, c) P 130 Cu, d) P 130 Ni

Fig. 2 IR spectrum of modified sample P 130 Co

Fig. 3 X-ray diffraction patterns of sample P130 and modified forms P130 Co, P130 Cu and P130 Ni

Finally, by both ways modified clay materials were applied to the tread rubber blends as fillers. The influence of these materials on the vulcanization characteristics of the blends was studied and impact on the physical-mechanical properties before and after aging and the resilience flexibility for the preparing vulcanizates were evaluated. The possibility of modified and organomodified clay products application in composite materials has been successfully demonstrated.

The obtained results of this work provide new knowledge on the use of modified and organomodified clay products as fillers.

Keywords: aluminosilicates, composite materials, fillers, spectral and thermal properties, vulcanization characteristics, physical-mechanical properties.

Acknowledgment:

This item is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.

This presentation was also created in the frame of the project Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass (CEGLASS), ITMS code is 313011R453, operational program Research and innovation, co-funded from European Regional Development Fund.